

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SSEKAMULI****FIRST NAME: BENJAMIN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Preparation for academic essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-9)
2. Rules of thumb for paper writing (EUCLID 2024, 13-14)
3. English variants: American Vs. British (EUCLID 2024, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
5. Citation (EUCLID 2024, 35-38)

WRITING A QUALIFYING ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

The recent advances in technology have immensely lifted the space for the wide sharing of research papers and, therefore, give an opportunity to researchers worldwide to get into the national, regional, and international arenas, thereby exposing their findings for the greater benefit of the communities. However, such writing requires standardisation of the papers to facilitate ease of readability alongside others. As I embarked on my journey to undertaking a Doctorate in Mediation and Conflict Resolution (DMCR), starting with making that critical decision, I understood the need to write and share my findings. Still, I was unaware of the level of detail required to produce a qualifying academic paper.

The course material provided for the first course in this journey exposes one to the basic understanding and key considerations for writing an academic essay. The course pack was revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma in 2024. Alongside this course pack was a video tutorial from Prof Laurent Cleenewerck, providing further guidance on preparing EUCLID standard Response Papers. The course pack highlights reading and researching critical aspects required before writing an academic essay since it helps acquire relevant information for understanding the topic and further developing the initial idea (EUCLID 2024, 7-9). Proper use of the various punctuation marks and

American and British English are presented, noting that they are more similar than different (EUCLID 2024, 25). Proper citation is featured as a means of giving credit to the author of the source of information and, therefore, a sure way to avoid plagiarism.

Having interacted with the materials provided for period one of this course, this response paper mainly presents preparation for academic essay writing, rules of thumb for paper writing, English styles: American Vs British, plagiarism, and citation as the five concepts learned.

2) PREPARATION FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

The first few paragraphs of the first chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack mention that academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2024, 7). From this statement, I noted four important elements: ideas, hypothesis, answers, and evidence. What comes to my mind is that one has an idea(s) that they would like to communicate. However, this idea needs to be tested in the form of a question(s) that require answers and, therefore, the need for evidence to back up the communication. I realise that these four elements seem to form the basis of an academic essay, and the preparation process must consider them beforehand.

I have learned that it is best to start early by allocating enough time to read and research the topic or ideas. At this point in time, the intention is to generate much information, which will lead to the refinement of the ideas and questions. Therefore, this requires writing every piece of information gathered concerning the idea. I believe this ultimately leads to a comprehensive understanding of the entire research and task ahead. This enables drawing up a plan of action on how the essay will be written with clarity on the questions to be responded to, the type of evidence required, and the kind of answers that will be communicated.

Once this is accomplished, I notice that the next important thing is reading and researching what to write (EUCLID 2024, 8-9). The knowledge and information acquired about the idea at hand and its relevance in responding to the questions is essential at this stage. I could add that it is important to identify who, in that profession, can help provide more relevant information.

Reading this, I came to appreciate that emphasis is put on spending time to look for relevant information since this provides evidence to support the arguments. I believe that this approach goes a long way, even for practitioners who do not intend to write essays, to help gather evidence to back up arguments. It will, therefore, be helpful to me all through.

3) RULES OF THUMB FOR PAPER WRITING

This is my first response paper, and while I was writing, I checked again and again on the suggested rules of thumb presented in the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack. Specifically, and agreeably so, is the first one that calls for stating the main thesis of the

paper at (or near) the beginning, preferably in the opening paragraph (EUCLID 2024, 13). I am convinced that this helps the reader to get to know what the content is all about and what to expect, which is good for attracting attention and connection as soon as possible.

I have noted the need to stay focused on the aspects being presented rather than providing a comprehensive overview. The fact that similar research can have variations in research findings may attract criticism of the literature and generate a lot of discussion, thereby deviating from the focus. While it is important to review literature, I learned that such deviations need to be avoided and keep focused on the assessment of the critical aspects of my research. Furthermore, clarity in writing is required. For the first time, I have found guidance on the length of paragraphs and sentences, which I find crucial for all my next papers. The key is to make sure things are simple and easy to read, keeping focus on the ideas being presented (EUCLID 2024, 13).

One thing to note is putting some dynamism to the text by avoiding simple things like starting paragraphs in the same manner or using the same words over again in the same sentence. Avoiding such helps the reader not to get bored. Importantly, giving credit to the source of information by appropriate citation is essential in paper writing. It avoids plagiarism of all forms and needs to be practiced at all costs (EUCLID 2024, 14).

4) ENGLISH VARIANTS: AMERICAN VS. BRITISH

Growing up and going through my pre-university education, I was unaware that English had variants. While at the university, I heard an English accent, which I was unfamiliar with, and I thought it was the language of those who were born and raised in towns. Later, I came to understand that it was American English, and even then, it never occurred to me that it was an English variant. I simply treated it as a fancy way of speaking English, which is common to those who attained their education in big cities. It is interesting for me to read that American English is currently the dominant influence on World English (EUCLID 2024, 25).

As I read this material, I found it interesting to learn the differences in the pronunciation of words with the same spellings in the same language, English. For words with different spellings yet with the same pronunciation, I used to think that one of the two was an error while the other was right. I never attributed this to American or British English. In so doing, I am certain that I have written essays with mixed English variants. It is informative, for me, to map the main categories of differences between the two English variants, and I need to be keen on using either/or as opposed to mixing both in one essay.

The basic ACA-401 video tutorial delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck is beneficial in setting this up right from the onset of essay writing to avoid mixing up the two English variants and to ensure consistency. I will uphold this during my paper writing, both as a student and as a practitioner.

5) PLAGIARISM

I recall the support and guidance that I received from my parents as a young boy and how I always attributed my being to that continuous nurturing. Behind me are great parents who worked hard to shape me, thus the credit. It is true that behind the enormous work of any researcher lies the efforts of other researchers, thus the need to recognise their efforts. I agree that using a source of information without crediting the author, the act of plagiarism, is not good and must not be practiced at any scale. I have noted that plagiarism is a serious academic offense and has serious consequences (EUCLID 2024, 34).

While it is right that plagiarism is common, my understanding is that it can be intended in cases where one is unethical and intends to claim originality of the ideas or unintentional in cases where one is unaware of the vice and how to avoid it. More interesting for me is owning and presenting a paper using someone who has been hired to write it, which amounts to plagiarism. Getting exposed to it at the very beginning of my studies gives me a great opportunity to avoid plagiarism during and after my studies.

Propper citing of the author, or the source of information is the only sure means to avoid plagiarism. I will endeavour to properly cite all sources of information used in this study and thereafter.

6) CITATION

While writing discussion papers or making presentations in my line of work, I have encountered several cases where the audience requested referencing. Verbally, I think citation and referencing have been used interchangeably, but reading this ACA-401/ACA-401D, I seem to understand the difference. While citation briefly mentions the source of information within the body of text with a view of giving credit to the source, referencing details the list of sources of information cited.

In this course pack, I have been exposed to the use of quotations when citing. I now understand that quotation marks are required when the exact words of the author being cited are written. In cases where the lines of quotation are few, the text is put between quotation marks. However, when the quotation lines are more than four, the text is indented, making it look like a separate short paragraph. In both cases, I notice that quotations need to be limited to cases where the original author uses language that brings out the meaning well or in a way that can easily persuade the intended audience for your paper (EUCLID 2024, 35-38).

To avoid many quotations, I noticed that paraphrasing is also allowed, in which case one must use their own words and styles to represent what the author originally wrote accurately. However, citation is also required in cases where paraphrasing has been adopted. Guidance on cases not requiring citation is also good; a thorough literature review should demonstrate that the information is common knowledge. This information is certainly relevant for me as I embark on my journey.

7) CONCLUSION

My admission to this program was received with mixed feelings of excitement and fear of not making time for the courses. And so, I needed some level of comfort and assurance. This very first course, and more specifically, the course material provided, enlightened me on what to expect and, therefore, gave me the level of comfort and assurance that I needed. I am pleased to mention that I have learned quite a lot of basics in the course materials (both the course pack and video), and I believe this course lays the foundation for the other courses.

From the beginning of the course, learning and being reminded of the ethical values of paper writing, the variants of English, punctuations, Latin abbreviations and expressions, and so much more has been of great value. This course has indeed rekindled my desire and willingness to learn new things. I look forward to the next course.

REFERENCES

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